

**RESULTS OF A PRACTICAL ANALYSIS OF A SOLAR
PHOTOVOLTAIC POWER PLANT CONNECTED IN ON-GRID MODE
IN JUNE**

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Abstract: It is being implemented rationally within the framework of the President's energy sector reform program and with his initiatives. Since our country is a sunny country, the solar photovoltaic method of using renewable resources is very effective. In this practical research article, methods of installing solar photovoltaic power plant and determination of efficiency, analysis of connection modes and dependence of produced electricity on air temperature are studied. The article also analyzed the modes of connecting inverters and revealed what types of inverters are effective in what conditions.

Key words: solar panel, intensity, light, sun, inverter, photo sensor, photovoltaic power stations, efficiency, environmentally friendly, PV modules, voltage, current, power, off-grid, on-grid, hybrid ,

Enter. Currently, large-scale installation of solar photovoltaic panels is being carried out across our Republic. This method of obtaining electricity does not require primary fuel resources and does not emit harmful gases and waste to our environment. Therefore, the solar photovoltaic (PV) system is the simplest and easiest to use for the production of electricity from renewable energy sources (M.Q. Shamshiddinov, 2023). Scientists have been working on increasing the

efficiency of solar panels for several years (Shamshiddinov Muhiddin Kadirjonovich, Alijanov Donyorbek Dilshodovich, Komilov Murodjon, 2023). Among solar cells, elements made of silicon occupy a special place from the point of view of their use on earth. of solar elements increased by 15-16% on the side of scientists of the former Soviet Union and the United States of America. New solar cells based on arsenide gallium phosphide gallium sulfide and telluride cadmium were introduced (B.E.Khayriddinov, N.S.Kholmirzayev, B.N. Sattorov, 2011).

It is not difficult to understand that increasing the efficiency of PV modules is becoming the most urgent issue of our day, as scientists all over the world are conducting scientific research (Hammad B, Al-Sardeah A, Al-Abed M, Nijmeh S, Al-Ghandoor A., 2017).

The of the solar photovoltaic cell based on gallium arsenide reached 25%, which means that it is 2 times less than the FIC of the solar thermal power plant. From the research, it can be understood that if the part of the sun's spectrum that passes without doing work in a semiconductor can be achieved with the help of multi-element (cascade) converters, it is possible to create an electron hole and convert it into the energy of photons that pass without being absorbed, and use it for a specific purpose. of such solar devices can reach 70-80% (B.E.Khayriddinov, N.S.Kholmirzayev, B.N.SATTOROV, 2011).

Solar photovoltaic stations are developing very widely in all developed countries of the world. The analysis results of a photovoltaic (PV) power plant connected to the network in the On-Grid mode with a nominal capacity of 2130.7 kW located in the eastern part of Turkey were studied. In 2017, this PV plant produced 3519.98 MW/h of energy. Average duty cycle, average final yield, system efficiency and power factor were found to be 4.53 hours/day, 81.15%, 18.86% and 13.18% respectively (Mete Cubukcu, Harun Gumus, 2020).

Figure 1. Annual electricity generation diagram of a 2130.7 kW rated solar photovoltaic power plant located in eastern Turkey.

Developing countries such as China have installed large amounts of renewable energy in the last eight years. According to the data, at the beginning of 2022, the total capacity of solar PV installations worldwide was 167.8 GW, which shows a growth of 21%. Demand for solar power generation capacity is expected to increase significantly over the next four years, from 254 GW in 2023 to 350 GW in 2026 (Meghraj Morey, Nitin Gupta, Man Mohan Garg, Ajay Kumar, 2023).

From the research results presented above, it can be understood that large-scale scientific and practical work is underway to improve the efficiency of PV modules. This is the first stage of the transition to environmentally friendly green energy, which is being rationally implemented within the framework of the President's energy sector reform program and initiatives. Since our country is a sunny country, the solar photovoltaic method of using renewable resources is very effective.

The total solar energy potential of our republic is estimated to be 51 billion tons of oil equivalent, and its technical potential is 176.8 million tons. This means that the absolute value of the solar energy falling on the land of Uzbekistan for a

year is much more than the verified hydrocarbon raw materials of the country. At present, only 0.3% of solar energy is utilized (S.Q. KAHAROV, H.O. JORAYEV, Y.Y. JAMILOV, 2021, Bukhara).

The alignment angle of solar PV modules is 34o degrees to azimuth for our Republic (I.A. Yuldoshev, E.B. Saitov, 2017), regardless of the connection mode, PV modules are installed in the same way. But the inverter device of the solar photovoltaic system is selected based on the needs of the customer. The inverter device of the system converts direct current generated by PV modules from sunlight into industrial current, i.e. alternating current. In solar PV modules, constant current is generated from sunlight and the constant current is accumulated in accumulators. Currently, 540 and 550 watt (W) solar PV modules are being installed in these capacities as they are very common.

Material and methods. The output parameters of 540 watt PV modules were measured in laboratory conditions at a temperature of 25o C, when the solar energy is 1000 J per 1 m², the voltage is $U_{max} = 45$ V, and the current is $I_{max} = 12$ A. The main parameter of PV modules is the voltage, which is produced without exceeding 50 volts. Depending on the capacity of the solar photovoltaic station system, the inverter device is selected. Depending on the input parameters of the inverter device, i.e. without increasing the input voltage from the panel, the value of the voltage coming from the solar panels is increased by connecting the panels in series. The solar panels are grouped according to the number of PV inputs of the inverter and the input power should be equalized as much as possible. If the power at the inputs is not equalized, the symmetrical operation mode of the inverter will be violated, and the possibility of burning devices will increase, and it will also lead to a violation of symmetry in networks.

Inverters are connected and operated in one of the following three modes according to the demand of the customer: off-grid, on-grid and hybrid (Lee JF, Rahim NA., 2013) (Barbosa de Melo K, Kitayama da Silva M, Lucas de Souza

Silva J, Costa TS, Villalva MG., 2017).

Off-grid mode, the solar photovoltaic station is managed independently of the grid. In this mode, a mini solar photovoltaic power station with a small capacity (a few kilowatts) is connected and used mainly for the lighting system. Since the system works independently of the network, it transfers the energy stored in the accumulator at night and on days without sunlight. This requires the introduction of a large number of accumulators to accumulate a large amount of electricity. Fulfillment of this requirement will increase the price of the mini photovoltaic system economically. For the reasons given above, it is a correct and

effective way to use the off-grid mode in order to satisfy the needs of consumers of small capacities. Off-grid mode is mainly designed for use in places where the power grid does not reach: country yards, mountain resorts and similar places. Figure 2 shows the scheme of connecting a solar photovoltaic station in Off-grid mode.

Figure 2. Scheme of solar photovoltaic plant connected in off-grid mode.

1- solar panel; 2- inverter; 3- accumulator; 4- consumer.

On-grid mode, the solar photovoltaic station is designed to work together with the grid. In the on-grid mode, a solar photovoltaic power station with a large capacity is connected and it is ensured that it works in parallel with the grid. Since the system works in parallel with the grid, the power of the consumer is not very

important to the power of the photovoltaic power plant that needs to be installed. An inverter connected in on-grid mode produces energy at the same level regardless of consumption. If the electricity generated from solar energy is not enough for the consumer, the inverter device takes the insufficient energy from the grid. If the generated electricity is more than the consumption, the inverter device transfers the excess electricity to the network. This makes it possible to generate more electricity during the day and transfer it to the state account, and to use the transferred energy at night. This mode of solar photovoltaic systems is suitable for enterprises and organizations that work mainly during the day. As with every work, there is a drawback to such a system. That is, it is used to reduce the load on the network only when there is electricity in the network. If we increase the number of on-grid solar photovoltaic power stations, we can achieve

a reduction in network outages.

Figure 3. Scheme of solar photovoltaic station connected in on-grid mode.

1- solar panel; 2- inverter; 3- network; 4- consumer.

When connected in hybrid mode, the solar photovoltaic station is designed to work together with the grid. In the hybrid mode, a small solar photovoltaic power

station is connected and works in parallel with the network. Since the system works in parallel with the network, the power of the consumer is required to match the power of the photovoltaic power plant to be installed. An inverter connected in hybrid mode produces energy at the same level regardless of consumption. If the electricity generated from solar energy is not enough for the consumer, the inverter device takes the insufficient energy from the battery and the network.

Figure 4. Scheme of solar photovoltaic plant connected in hybrid mode.

1- solar panel; 2- inverter; 3- accumulator; 4- network; 5- consumer.

If the produced electricity is more than the consumption, the inverter device accumulates the excess electricity in the accumulator and transfers the surplus to the network. This makes it possible to generate more electricity during the day and transfer it to the state account, and at night to use the accumulator and the transferred energy. This mode of solar photovoltaic systems is suitable for enterprises and organizations that work mainly during the day. The advantage of this mode over the others is that the system will continue to work if there is a power outage in the network.

Research results. Currently, many organizations and enterprises throughout our country are installing on-grid solar photovoltaic systems. The angle of alignment of solar PV modules is 34o degrees to azimuth for our Republic,

regardless of the connection mode, PV modules are installed in the same way.

Figure 5. Location of a 50 kW solar photovoltaic power plant located in the city of Andijan.

The solar modules are placed in series and are placed touching each other. Because the output parameters of one solar module of 540 watts were measured in laboratory conditions, i.e. at a temperature of 25°C, when the solar energy falls to 1000 J per 1 m², the voltage is $U_{max} = 45$ V, and the current is $I_{max} = 12$ A. The main parameter of PV modules is the voltage, which is produced without exceeding 50 volts. The panel input voltage of the inverter device is on average 750-1100 volts. Therefore, we have to connect a certain number of PV modules in series. However, the space between the rows should be placed in such a way that they do not overshadow each other on any day of the year. The inverter device is installed in a place where sunlight does not fall, not far from the PV modules.

Figure 6. Location of a 50 kW inverter device for a solar photovoltaic power plant with a nominal capacity of 50 kW located in the city of Andijan.

To analyze the electricity we produced from this inverter unit in June, we studied the values of the first 13 days.

Table

Results of a practical analysis of a solar photovoltaic power plant connected in On-Grid mode in June

№	Date	Weather condition		Air temperature		Produced electricity, kW*h
				Night, °C	Day, °C	
1	01.06.2023		Partly cloudy	+20	+30	202
2	02.06.2023		Partly cloudy	+20	+31	215
3	03.06.2023		A little cloudy	+19	+32	240

4	04.06.2023		Sunny	+18	+34	235
5	05.06.2023		Strong cloudy	+20	+33	205
6	06.06.2023		Partly cloudy	+20	+34	230
7	07.06.2023		A little cloudy	+20	+36	227
8	08.06.2023		Sunny	+21	+38	232
9	09.06.2023		Sunny	+21	+39	231
10	10.06.2023		Sunny	+23	+38	208
11	11.06.2023		Strong cloudy	+23	+36	210
12	12.06.2023		Strong cloudy	+22	+36	150
13	13.06.2023		Thunderstorm	+24	+34	148

Figure 7. Diagram of electricity produced by a 50 kW solar photovoltaic

power plant located in the city of Andijan from June 1 to June 13.

Conculusion. The time for the analysis was chosen so that the weather was different every day. There were sunny days, cloudy days, and even rainy days. The obtained results show that the air temperature exceeding $+35^{\circ}\text{C}$ on a sunny day causes the efficiency of the solar photovoltaic power plant to decrease.

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